

Study of Fiber Bragg Grating spectral overlapping for laser structures

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Abstract—In this paper, different parameters of the spectral overlapping filtering technique have been analyzed for laser structures. Despite the promising preliminary experimental results obtained using this filtering technique, the optimization of the FBG parameters to reduce the bandwidth of the achieved filter depending on the fiber laser requirements and configuration, should be performed. The simulated results have been confirmed during the experimental tests, where the same bandwidths and power evolutions have been measured using a ring laser configuration. This technique has been also tested for very narrow filtering purposes by achieving the Single Longitudinal Mode operation with a ring cavity of $L \approx 8 m$, using only two uniform FBGs.

Index Terms—Fiber lasers, Erbium, Single Longitudinal Mode, Fiber Bragg Grating, Laser stabilization

I. INTRODUCTION

For several applications based on fiber lasers [1]–[3], it is required to have a very stable source that does not limit the final system performance. Some of these applications such as communication systems based on Wavelength Division Multiplexing (WDM), optical fiber sensors or spectroscopy are based on very stable lasers. This kind of sources must operate in the Single Longitudinal Mode (SLM) regime to achieve the required stability. Within a fiber laser, the number of the resulting laser modes is determined by two factors: the optical cavity and the optical filtering element. In this way, a SLM operation can be achieved by shortening the cavity or narrowing the optical filter. Therefore, the gain usually has to be high to produce the oscillation condition. This effect is critical when working with low erbium concentration fibers, increasing the length of the laser cavity. As a consequence, an ultra-narrow optical filter has to be included within the cavity to remove the multiple longitudinal modes and ensure a SLM operation.

Fiber Bragg Gratings have been widely employed in fiber lasers as optical filters but, in many applications, they have been combined with other optical techniques to achieve ultra-narrow filters: saturable absorbers [4], multi-ring loops [5] or employing FBGs as self-injection feedback elements [6]. In [7], [8] a combination of a FBG and phase shift FBG (PSFBG), has been employed as a narrow band pass filter. Some of these techniques increase the setup complexity, reducing its flexibility to achieve multiwavelength lasers.

This work has been supported by the project TEC2010-20224-C02-02 and grant AP2009-1403.

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A narrow filtering technique based on the spectral overlapping of two uniform FBGs has been proposed in [9] to achieve a SLM operation in short linear fiber lasers. The spectral overlapping of FBGs is not a new optical technique and it has been used before for some applications such as the design of pulsed fiber lasers [10] or FBG interrogation [11]. Nevertheless, the partial spectral overlapping of two uniform FBGs to achieve ultra-narrow equivalent filter bandwidths is an original and flexible technique that can be applied to different fiber laser configurations, even when long cavity lengths are required.

Although the spectral overlapping technique has been successfully employed in a proof-of-concept device [9], an exhaustive study of this filtering method is required to analyze its benefits and limitations. This study will allow a better optimization of the FBG parameters (reflectivities, length, and bandwidth) to reduce the final bandwidth of the designed filter. In this work, several aspects of the FBG spectral overlapping have been studied both theoretical and experimentally. Based on these results, an erbium doped fiber ring laser with a cavity length of $L \approx 8 m$ has been experimentally verified, even reaching the SLM regime caused by the spectral selectivity of the proposed technique.

II. SPECTRAL OVERLAPPING

The spectral overlapping technique is based on a pair of FBGs of matched Bragg wavelengths, being one slightly detuned and keeping its reflection spectra partially overlapped with the other. In this way, the whole spectral overlapped response of both FBGs becomes narrower than the ones associated with the two individual FBGs. When introduced in an active structure, the resulting laser output becomes also narrower (lower bandwidth), reducing the number of active longitudinal modes and even allowing to reaching the Single Longitudinal Mode (SLM) operation.

By employing this structure, as the detuning increases (maintaining some spectral overlapping) the equivalent filter bandwidth becomes narrower. The main drawback of this scheme is the power drop due to the equivalent reflection reduction of the overlapped filter. This effect can be minimized by employing FBGs with a higher reflectivity (even being saturated) because their side slopes are steeper, what implies that, maintaining the same bandwidth, a higher equivalent reflectivity can be achieved. However, their tuning process becomes more challenging. Trying to study these particularities, several simulations have been performed to analyze the

evolution of the combined filter response when different FBGs and displacements are employed.

Fig. 1. Spectral overlapping of FBGs with different reflectivities (a). Achieved bandwidth (b) and reflectivity (c) during the wavelength displacement.

III. SIMULATIONS

The combined filter response is mainly driven by the edges of the main lobe of both FBG spectra and their relative wavelength displacement. By employing FBGs with steeper edges (i.e. high reflectivity or longer FBGs), their overlapped response bandwidth will experience a fast drop as their wavelength displacement increases. Thus, lower bandwidths can be achieved when using FBGs with steeper edges.

The individual FBG spectra have been simulated using the T-matrix method [9] while their combined response has been obtained by numerically displacing one spectrum before computing their product. One of the two matched FBGs has been displaced until the main peaks overlap becomes lower than the secondary lobes. These displacements have been calculated for two FBG pairs of $L = 10$ mm length but with different reflectivities ($R_1 \approx 99\%$ and $R_2 \approx 84\%$ as shown in Fig.1, a). At lower displacements, the combined filter reflectivity and bandwidth are still comparable to a single FBG; however, when the edges of the main lobes are close, a great reduction on bandwidth and reflectivity is produced. This effect is more drastic when high reflectivity FBGs are employed as can be noticed in Fig.1, where the achieved 95% bandwidth (b) and reflectivity (c) of the combined filters have been plotted as a function of their wavelength displacement (difference between Bragg wavelength of both FBGs). As can be noticed, the achieved bandwidth of the combined filter is lower for higher reflectivity FBG pairs, what allow a best spectral selectivity (filter narrowing) when working with saturated FBGs. Particularly, in the depicted simulations, the minimum achieved bandwidth for $L = 10$ mm FBGs

is $BW_H \approx 4$ pm for the higher reflectivity FBG pair and $BW_L \approx 6$ pm for the lower reflectivity pair. But, as the reflectivity of the main FBG lobe increases, this effect is also reproduced for the secondary lobes, what limits the maximum wavelength displacement and, consequently, also limits the filter narrowing. This effect can be reduced by employing apodized FBGs, although apodization functions usually gives rise to smoother main lobe edges, what also limits the filter narrowing.

Fig. 2. Reflection spectra of FBGs of different lengths (top). Relation between the achieved bandwidth and its reflectivity for different FBG lengths from 4 to 22 mm (bottom).

In addition to the reflectivity, the FBG length has to be also considered in the design process. Longer FBGs of the same reflectivity have steeper main lobes, but their secondary lobes have the same reflectivity, what benefits the filter narrowing. In Fig.2 (top) several FBGs of different lengths but the same reflectivity ($R \approx 95\%$) are depicted. When the FBG length increases, the main lobe of the FBG becomes narrower and steeper, increasing its edges slope. This situation can be useful for filtering purposes because their combination can be also steeper.

Although, narrower combined filter bandwidths can be achieved by employing long FBGs with a high reflectivity, as their main lobes become steeper, their tuning process can be more complicated: given that there is a huge reflectivity variation for a small wavelength displacement. In Fig.2 (bottom), the achieved filter bandwidth is compared to its reflectivity for different FBG lengths. This graph gives an idea of how abrupt is the tuning process depending on the chosen FBGs. On the contrary, when the filtering requirements are not so strict, lower FBG lengths (and/or reflectivities) can be employed to make the manufacturing process easier and improve the final laser stability against external perturbations (such as vibrations).

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A ring laser scheme has been employed for the experimental verification of the proposed technique (Fig.3, top). In order to reach the best performance (narrower laser bandwidth) and based on simulations, a combination of two long FBGs of $L = 24 \text{ mm}$ with a high reflectivity have been employed as the filtering element of this laser. This worst-case scenario has been proposed to be experimentally analyzed to verify the previous simulations. Two circulators have been connected in series and they have been also spliced to both FBGs to get the combination of their reflection spectra. The resulting filter is the partial overlap of both FBG reflection spectra. The employed FBGs have been characterized using a high resolution Optical Spectrum Analyzer (BOSA-C, Argon-Photonics) and one spectrum is depicted against its simulated fitted model in Fig.3 (bottom).

Fig. 3. Ring laser setup based on the overlapping of two FBGs (top). Spectrum of one FBG measured using the BOSA and its simulated model (bottom).

A FBG has been stretched using a motor stage (Newport MM4005) while the other was fixed. Several stretching sweeps have been performed using different pump powers. Since determining the Bragg wavelength difference of two partially overlapped FBGs is inaccurate, all sweeps have been started at the minimum overlapped point, where the cavity starts lasing. For the employed FBG pair, this point corresponds to the SLM operation. Based on a fixed wavelength displacement of $\Delta\lambda \approx 2.5 \text{ pm}$, several increments have been applied to a FBG as both spectra became more overlapped.

In order to measure the spectral range where the longitudinal modes can oscillate, the laser output has been held for a time interval, obtaining the probability distribution of the laser emission. These measurements are directly related to the equivalent spectral shape of the filtering device. For

Fig. 4. 20 dB laser bandwidth against the wavelength difference between FBGs for different pump powers (top). Output laser power against the wavelength difference (bottom).

each step, the laser output has been held in the BOSA for $t = 3 \text{ min}$. This time has been set large enough to obtain the statistical behavior of the laser, but also short enough to minimize the errors due to environmental changes such as vibration or temperature. Several factors contribute in these bandwidth measurements such as the number of modes, mode hopping or external vibrations that can influence the final laser performance.

In Fig.4 (top), the measured laser bandwidth is depicted as a function of the wavelength displacement of the FBG for different pump powers. As the overlapped spectral area is reduced, the output laser bandwidth also becomes narrower. The same behavior has been noticed for different pump powers, being the main difference in the starting point: a lower pump power requires a higher equivalent reflectivity, thus, the starting displacement must be lower. The evolution of the laser power during the strain sweep is also depicted in Fig.4 (bottom) for a constant pump power. As the reflectivity of the combined filter decreases (while the laser bandwidth is also reduced) the output power also decreases. This power reduction is higher at lower laser bandwidths (higher displacements).

Despite the laser output power drop due to the combined filter reflectivity reduction, when employing FBGs with a very steep spectral response, extremely narrow filters can be achieved based on these technique. Particularly, for the chosen ring laser structure (with a total length of $L \approx 8 \text{ m}$), SLM operation has been achieved for different pump powers.

The SLM operation was verified with a heterodyne detection system using an Optical Converter (HP11982A) and an Electric Spectrum Analyzer (HP8592L). The laser output was combined with the signal of a Tunable Laser Source (TLS, Agilent 8164B) using a 3 dB coupler, whose wavelength has been placed close to the laser output. In Fig.5 (top), a capture with a single peak is shown associated with the different tested pump powers, proving the SLM operation of the laser, which is achieved at the wavelength of the matched FBGs ($\lambda_B \approx 1550.5 \text{ nm}$). However, when both FBGs are more overlapped, the laser begins to operate in multimode regime, as shown in Fig.5 (bottom).

Fig. 5. SLM operation at different pump powers (top) and multimode operation (bottom) of the ring laser measured with the heterodyne detection system.

The achieved results exhibit the capability of the spectral overlapping technique to reach very narrow filters for laser structures. Particularly, by employing FBGs with steeper main lobes, extremely narrow filters capable of reaching SLM operation even with very low modal spacing ($\Delta\lambda \approx 0.1 \text{ pm}$) can be obtained. However, in order to improve the laser stability, when working with very narrow filters, additional strategies are required to isolate the vibration and/or temperature variations of the FBGs, such as fixing both FBGs to a host material. Besides, by fixing both FBGs to the same host material, the laser output will be modified according to the FBGs' strain and temperature, being able to vary its wavelength several nm.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, several aspects of the FBG spectral overlapping technique have been studied both simulated and experimentally. The achieved results can help on the design of new laser structures by showing the final performance of two uniform FBGs employed as a combined filtering element. Despite the fact that both output power and bandwidth are the most important features in the laser design, other practical issues must be taken into account in the manufacturing process such

as external noise isolation (such as vibration) or flexibility of the tuning process. The simulated results have been confirmed during the experimental tests, where the same bandwidths and power evolutions have been measured using a ring laser configuration employing two partially overlapped FBGs as the filtering element. This technique has been also tested for very narrow filtering purposes by achieving the Single Longitudinal Mode operation in a ring cavity of $L \approx 8 \text{ m}$ only using two uniform FBGs. In addition, the spectral overlapping is a flexible technique that can be employed in different fiber laser structures and it is capable of achieving real high performance devices, with the suitable manufacture and packaging processes.

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